

Adsorption of Acids by Cocoanut Charcoal and Acetylene Carbon.

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Experiments with Cocoanut Charcoal.

These experiments were performed during 1922-23, but owing to certain interruption it was not possible to put together the results immediately then.

There are not any results known to me with reference to the adsorption of acids by cocoanut charcoal covering the same field as the investigation communicated in this paper. Some of the experiments on adsorption by cocoanut charcoal were made using the charcoal prepared from the inside kernel and not from the outside shell. Firth (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 926) in his study of adsorption of ammonia by cocoanut charcoal used the cocoanut shell for preparing the adsorbent. Driver and Firth (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 2409) in their study of adsorption of saturated vapours by charcoal used cocoanut charcoal prepared from both the shell and the fruit. But these and other investigators, I have come across, did not deal with acids in solution. In my experiments I have used the charcoal prepared from the outside shell of cocoanut and dealt with organic and inorganic acids in aqueous solution.

The experiments here described were undertaken to study the behaviour of cocoanut charcoal prepared from the outside shell of coconuts. It was also the intention to see if any general relation existed between the chemical constitution or the physical constants of the acids and the degree of adsorbability by a given adsorbent. Since the completion of the experiments described below, I have come across a paper by Fromageot and Wurmser (*Compt. rend.*, 1924, 179, 972) who have investigated the relation between the degree of adsorption and the ionisation constant as well as the number of carboxyl groups of an acid. Though they did not use cocoanut charcoal, I find it interesting to give below, in the course of the

discussion of my results, a summary of their observations and show how they compare with mine.

Preparation of Coconut Charcoal.—The coconut shells used were those of ordinary kind obtainable in Madras. After removal of rasp, the shells were broken into small pieces. The broken pieces were charred well-covered with sand in an iron tray over a ring-burner. It took 3 to 4 hours to char all the pieces thoroughly. Out of every 100 gms. of original shell pieces, 30 to 40 gms. of charred shell pieces were obtained. They were powdered coarsely at first and finely afterwards. The powder was sieved through a fine mesh (90 to 100 meshes per inch), dried for 12 hrs. in an air-oven at 150° and cooled in a desiccator before use. The density of the powder was found to be 1.45 gms. per c. c. The ash in the charcoal was found to be 1.18 per cent. The extraction of the charcoal with concentrated hydrochloric acid reduced the ash to 0.68 per cent.

Preliminary Experiments.—Experiments were undertaken to determine the effect of time of shaking on the rate of adsorption, and it was found that the amount of oxalic acid adsorbed by coconut charcoal increased with increased periods of continuous shaking at first rapidly and then slowly. It was further found that in practice letting the solution stand with the charcoal for 5 to 7 days with occasional shaking, say 3 or 4 times a day, gave satisfactory equilibrium concentration. In the following experiments the solution was allowed to stand in well-stoppered bottles for a week in contact with the charcoal with occasional shaking in room temperature (27°–30°).

Experimental Details. The purest specimens of acids available in the laboratory were used in each case. The solutions of required concentrations were prepared (five dilutions from about 0.20 molar to 0.05 molar) and put in stoppered bottles. In similar bottles weighed amounts (about 1 gm.) of charcoal were introduced, and then 50 c.c. of each of the solutions were added, and allowed to stand for a week with occasional shaking. The original solutions also were allowed to stand in the stoppered bottles for the same period. Afterwards both the original solution and the solution added to the charcoal were titrated carefully using standard dilute baryta solution. For titration measured quantities of the clear solution over the charcoal layer were taken with a graduated pipette.

Experimental Result. From the experimental results so obtained I calculated the values of the equilibrium molar concentration of

Fig. 2.

the solution after adsorption and of the number of millimoles of solute adsorbed per gram of charcoal. The results were plotted and graphs drawn (Figs. 1 & 2). The graphs show that, within the dilutions studied, the adsorption of most of the acids examined follow the adsorption equation,

$$m = a C^{1/k}$$

where m is the number of millimoles of solute adsorbed per gram of charcoal ;
 C is the equilibrium molar concentration of solution after adsorption ;
 and a and k are constants.

I calculated the mean values of a and k for the cases examined. I have tabulated the values of C , m , a and k obtained (Table I).

TABLE I.
Cocconut Charcoal.

Serial No.	Name of acid.	Expt. No.	C	m	a	k
I.	Formic acid	1	0.2727	0.756	1.16	2.88
		2	0.2090	0.686		
		3	0.1592	0.674		
		4	0.0913	0.489		
		5	0.0499	0.479		
II.	Acetic acid	1	0.2281	0.645	1.38	2.96
		2	0.2000	0.805		
		3	0.1310	0.699		
		4	0.1174	0.656		
		5	0.0575	0.526		
III.	Propionic acid	1	0.2136	0.886	1.48	2.94
		2	0.1617	0.808		
		3	0.1281	0.760		
		4	0.0839	0.628		
		5	0.0384	0.494		

Serial No.	Name of acid.	Expt. No.	C	m	a	k
IV.	Butyric acid	1	0.2079	0.984		
		2	0.1603	0.981		
		3	0.1180	0.851	1.72	2.90
		4	0.0776	0.736		
		5	0.0370	0.609		
V.	Valeric acid	1	0.1976	0.758		
		2	0.1519	0.638		
		3	0.1099	0.576	1.15	2.81
		4	0.0702	0.488		
		5	0.0359	0.372		
VI.	Mono-chloroacetic acid	1	0.1993	0.981		
		2	0.1477	0.881		
		3	0.1046	0.855	1.58	3.22
		4	0.0698	0.701		
		5	0.0336	0.584		
VII.	Dichloroacetic acid	1	0.2204	0.819		
		2	0.1690	0.749		
		3	0.1277	0.665	1.51	2.54
		4	0.0920	0.603		
		5	0.0453	0.454		
VIII.	Trichloroacetic acid	1	0.1897	0.366		
		2	0.1478	0.336		
		3	0.1101	0.306	0.68	2.77
		4	0.0719	0.242		
		5	0.0344	0.236		
IX.	Mono-bromoacetic acid	1	0.2060	1.077		
		2	0.1092	0.900		
		3	0.1016	0.868	1.85	3.00
		4	0.0692	0.761		
		5	0.0336	0.609		

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Serial No.	Name of acid.	Expt. No.	<i>G</i>	<i>m</i>	<i>a</i>	<i>k</i>
X.	Dibrom-acetic acid	1	0.2908	1.800		
		2	0.2927	1.079		
		3	0.1834	1.115	2.83	3.05
		4	0.1101	0.769		
		5	0.0857	0.590		
XI.	Hydroxy-acetic acid	1	0.2862	0.364		
		2	0.1859	0.374		
		3	0.1388	0.289	0.47	5.14
		4	0.0983	0.311		
		5	0.0514	0.285		
XII.	Dimethyl-acetic acid	1	0.2189	0.774		
		2	0.1780	0.754		
		3	0.1913	0.655	1.19	3.42
		4	0.0948	0.600		
		5	0.0418	0.478		
XIII.	<i>iso</i> -Propyl-acetic acid	1	0.1694	0.556		
		2	0.1394	0.501		
		3	0.1191	0.478	1.07	2.88
		4	0.1008	0.496		
		5	0.0680	0.357		
XIV.	Oxalic acid	1	0.1869	0.506		
		2	0.1525	0.474		
		3	0.1122	0.440	0.79	3.70
		4	0.0708	0.399		
		5	0.0307	0.305		
XV.	Hydrochloric acid	1	0.2485	0.353		
		2	0.1717	0.364		
		3	0.1078	0.306	0.38	19.1
		4	0.0772	0.310		
		5	0.0328	0.311		

Serial No.	Name of acid.	Expt. No.	<i>C</i>	<i>m</i>		
XVI.	Hydrobromic acid	1	0.2554	0.328		
		2	0.1986	0.301		
		3	0.1495	0.278	0.39	7.12
		4	0.1049	0.270		
		5	0.0463	0.243		
XVII.	Nitric acid	1	0.2246	0.627		
		2	0.1809	0.263		
		3	0.1339	0.272	0.35	5.69
		4	0.0840	0.273		
		5	0.0407	0.238		
XVIII.	Sulphuric acid	1	0.2831	0.112		
		2	0.1667	0.115		
		3	0.1169	0.113	0.12	23.8
		4	0.0720	0.109		
		5	0.0351	0.101		
XIX.	Phosphoric acid	1	0.2389	0.291		
		2	0.1902	0.245		
		3	0.1462	0.202	2.40	0.71
		4	0.0937	0.089		
		5	0.0533	0.042		

Discussion of Results.—The results were examined to see if there is any well-marked relation between the chemical constitution or the physical constants of acids and their degree of adsorbability or the

values of a and k with reference to the adsorbent used, namely, cocoanut charcoal. The following points are worth noting in this connection. The adsorption isotherms of mineral acids approximate more towards straight lines than those of organic acids within the range of concentrations studied. The values of k for formic acid and its homologues are nearly equal. The value of k is greater generally for strong mineral acids than for weak organic acids (*cf.* hydrochloric with acetic acid). In the series from formic to butyric acid the values of a increase, while for valeric acid the value of a is smaller than that for butyric acid. Substitutions in the acids affect both a and k (*cf.* the substituted acetic acids), a being more susceptible than k . Repeated halogenation seems at first to enhance and then to diminish the values of both a and k of acetic acid. Chlorine, bromine and hydroxyl substitutions have different effects on the degree of adsorption of acetic acid. While the values of a for nitric, hydrochloric and hydrobromic acid are practically the same, the value of a for sulphuric acid is much less and that for phosphoric acid is much more. Phosphoric acid, though a weak acid, is not adsorbed to a greater extent than the strong mineral acids. The degree of adsorption of organic acids is generally greater than that of mineral acids. The adsorbability increases from formic to butyric acid but decreases from butyric to valeric acid. Increase in the number of carboxyl groups lowers the adsorption of the acid (*cf.* acetic and oxalic acid). There seems to be no general relation between the ionisation constants or the molecular structure of acids and the degree of adsorbability or the values of a and k of those acids.

Fromageot and Wurmser (*loc. cit.*) have found that there is no simple relation between the degree of adsorption of different acids and their electrolytic dissociation constants. With this observation my results agree. They also found that the adsorbability increased with the number of carboxyl groups by comparison of acetic, succinic, oxalic and citric acid. My results regarding acetic and oxalic acid with cocoanut charcoal and with acetylene carbon show a contrary effect in the former case but a similar effect in the latter (see below). I have not used succinic and citric acid in my experiments. They have further found that salts have a smaller degree of adsorption than that of the corresponding acids. I have not dealt with salts at all in my investigations so as to be able to make such comparison.

Experiments with Acetylene Carbon.

Experimental Details.—When these experiments were being conducted, it was thought desirable to try some other adsorbent; and acetylene carbon was tried at the suggestion of Prof. W. Erlam Smith. The acetylene carbon used was prepared by cooling a smoky acetylene flame (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3.

The carbon so obtained was collected, powdered and dried for 12 hrs. in an air-oven at 150°. It was found to contain 2.82 per cent. ash. The aqueous extract of the carbon was neutral to litmus. The adsorption of acetic and oxalic acid was tried with the help of this carbon and it was found that the concentrations of the solutions increased on being allowed to stand in contact with acetylene carbon (Table II).

TABLE II.
Acetylene Carbon.

Name of acid.	Expt. No.	C	m
Oxalic acid	1	0'480	-0'48
	2	0'217	-0'84
	3	0'107	-0'47
	4	0'026	-0'40
	5	0'023	-0'58
Acetic acid	1	1'260	-1'10
	2	0'292	-1'11
	3	0'262	-1'23
	4	0'226	-1'10
	5	0'181	-1'09
	6	0'126	-1'20
	7	0'111	-1'20
	8	0'096	-1'92
	9	0'085	-2'30

Discussion of Results.—It seems probable that more water was adsorbed by acetylene carbon than the acid adsorbed by it. The amount of the solute adsorbed is less, the more dilute the solution.

Pickless (*Chem. News*, 1920, 121, 49) found in the case of wood charcoal and acetic acid solution that the ratio of

C_{charcoal} (i.e., m) to C_{water} (i.e., C) varied from +1'76 to +2'6

depending upon the concentration of the solution. I find that (1) in the case of acetylene carbon and acetic acid solution, the ratio $m/C = -1$ to -25 , and (2) in the case of cocoanut charcoal and acetic acid solution, the ratio $m/C = +4$ to $+10$. Pickles (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 1278) found that alkali halides were negatively adsorbed by wood charcoal.

Summary.

(1) Experiments were conducted in order to see if there is any simple relation between the degree of adsorption of acids and the chemical constitution or the physical constants of those acids. In these experiments cocoanut shell charcoal was used as the adsorbent.

(2) It was found that there was no direct relation between the degree of adsorption and the conductivity constants or the molecular structure of the acids examined.

(3) For the range of dilution studied (about 0.20 to 0.05 molar) the adsorption was in close agreement in most cases with the adsorption equation, $m = C^{1/k}$. For practical purposes m and C give respectively the concentrations of the solute in charcoal and in water in moles per kilogram. The adsorption isotherms of mineral acids approximate more towards straight lines than those of organic acids.

(4) It was found that the values of k for formic acid and its homologues were practically the same.

(5) The values of k were found to be greater for strong mineral acids than for weak organic and inorganic acids.

(6) The values of a were found first to increase and then to decrease in the series from formic to valeric acid.

(7) The values of a were found to be approximately the same for hydrochloric, hydrobromic and nitric acid.

(8) The nature and number of substitutions in an acid affect both a and k , a being affected to a greater extent than k .

(9) There seems to be no quantitative relation, however, between a or k and the ionisation constants or the molecular disposition of the acids.

(10) Increase in the number of carboxyl groups tends to lower the degree of adsorption in the case of cocoanut charcoal.

(11) Among the acids examined, sulphuric acid is least adsorbed. This may be so because of its great affinity for water.

(12) While the adsorption is positive in the case of cocoanut charcoal, the adsorption is negative in the case of acetylene carbon. That is, in the former case the solute is preferentially adsorbed, while in the latter case the solvent is preferentially adsorbed.

It seems desirable to pursue these experiments further especially with acetylene carbon, which would have been done already but for the unfortunate interruption referred to above. I hope to publish soon another paper on the adsorption of acetylene carbon.

I wish to thank Prof. W. Erlam Smith for the kind encouragement he always accorded to me.